

3. F. G. MANN and B. C. SAUNDERS, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Longman, New York, 1936, p. 365.
4. E. L. HIRST and J. K. N. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1959.
5. R. KHUN, H. TRISCHMANN and I. LOW, *Angew. Chem.*, 1955, 67, 32.
6. A. ULUBELEN, M. MISKI, P. NEUMAN and T. J. MABRY, *Lloydia*, 1979, 42, 262.
7. S. F. EL-NAGGAR and R. W. DOSKOTCH, *Lloydia*, 1979, 42, 126.
8. A. ULUBELEN, T. J. MABRY and Y. AYNHEHI, *Lloydia*, 1979, 42, 624.

Isolation of Hordenine from *Desmodium floribundum* G. Don.

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DESMODIUM (Leguminosae) is a large genus of perennial or annual herbs or shrubs found throughout the tropical and subtropical regions of the world. About thirtyeight species belonging to this genus are known to occur in India^{1,2}. The extracts of different parts of the members of this genus are well known for their medicinal uses in the indigenous system of medicine for a variety of ailments¹.

Earlier work on the alkaloids of a number of *Desmodium* species by Ghosal and coworkers* shows that this genus elaborates mainly simple indole and β -phenylethylamine alkaloids some of which elicit interesting pharmacodynamic properties. In view of this observation and the absence of any published report on the alkaloids of *Desmodium floribundum*, this plant was collected from Ranikhet (U.P.) area and taken up for investigation of its alkaloids. Separation of alkaloids from the alcoholic extract of the whole plant of *D. floribundum* following usual procedure⁴, chromatography of the total alkaloid fraction over silica gel column and elution with ethyl acetate-methanol (97 : 3) mixture furnished a homogenous solid which crystallised from benzene as colourless plates, m.p. 173°. The compound responded to Beilstein test for halogens, phosphomolybdic acid test for phenols and analysed for the molecular formula, C₁₀H₁₅NO.HCl. Its uv spectrum ($\lambda_{\max}$ 224, 227 nm; ϵ 7330, 2200) resembled that of *p*-cresol, its spectrum showed band for phenolic hydroxyl (3450 cm⁻¹) and ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃ + CD₃OD) showed signals for four aromatic hydrogens of a 1,4-disubstituted phenyl nucleus (δ 7.11 and 6.78, 2H, d each, J 8Hz), four aliphatic hydrogens of two vicinal methylenes around δ 3.14 as multiplets and two methyl groups bound to a protonated nitrogen as a six-proton singlet at δ 2.89. Mass spectrum of the compound showed the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 165 (4%) corresponding to

the free base, C₁₀H₁₅NO, a significant ion peak at *m/z* 107 (9%) due to hydroxytropylium cation and the base peak at *m/z* 58 (CH₂=N⁺Me₂) characteristic of dimethylaminoethyl side chain⁵. The data indicated the alkaloid to be hordenine hydrochloride (*N,N*-dimethyltyramine hydrochloride) which was confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p. and tlc) of the derived free base with authentic sample.

The notoriety of chloroform for conversion of alkamines to their hydrochlorides is well known^{6,7} and the isolation of hordenine as its hydrochloride is presumably due to the use of this solvent for extraction of alkaloids.

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References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 94.
2. "The Wealth of India : Raw Materials", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1952, Vol. 3, p. 41.
3. S. GHOSAL and R. S. SRIVASTAVA, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, 12, 193 and references cited therein.
4. M. SAHAI and A. B. RAY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1980, 45, 3265.
5. K. K. SETH, V. B. PANDEY, A. B. RAY, B. DASGUPTA and A. H. SHAH, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1979, 744.
6. T. A. HENRY, "The Plant Alkaloids", J & A Churchill Ltd., London, 1949, p. 636.
7. A. B. RAY, Y. OSHIMA, H. HIKINO and C. KABUTO, *Heterocycl.*, 1982, 19, 1233.

Chemistry of *Salvia lanata* Roxb.

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IN previous communications¹⁻³, we reported the isolation and characterisation of some di- and tri-terpenoidal components from the petrol extract of the whole plant (aerial parts and roots) of *Salvia lanata*⁴. This paper reports the isolation and identification of three pentacyclic triterpenes from the chloroform extract of defatted plant materials. Air dried and powdered whole plant (aerial parts

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and roots) of *Salvia lanata* Roxb. was soxhletted with light petrol (b.p. 60-80°) and chloroform in succession for 48 h each. The residue from chloroform extract was chromatographed over silica gel, elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity.

The concentrate of light petrol-benzene (1 : 1) eluate-fractions afforded a solid crystallised from petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1), m.p. 184-85°, [α]_D + 80° (CHCl₃). Its identity with α -amyrin was established by direct comparison (co-tlc, co-ir and m.m.p.) with an authentic sample⁵.

Further elution of the column with benzene furnished another triterpene having m.p. 233-34°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3300 cm⁻¹; m/z 442 (M⁺), 234, 207, 203, and 189. It was identified as uvaol by comparative studies (m.m.p., co-ir and co-tlc) with an authentic sample⁶ and through the preparation of acetate, m.p. 157°.

The fraction eluted with benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) yielded a solid which on repeated crystallisation from methanol furnished colourless solid, m.p. 270-72°; [α]_D + 80° (CHCl₃). It responded to Leibermann-Burchard† test for triterpene. The ir spectrum of the compound showed bands at $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700 (carbonyl), 1695 (carbonyl) and 1640 cm⁻¹ (unsaturation); methyl ester, m.p. 190-92°. The mass spectrum of the compound registered the molecular ion peak at m/z 454 along with other significant peaks at m/z 248 (base peak), 205, 203 and 202.

Finally, the identity of this triterpene as ursonic acid has been confirmed by the usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample⁷.

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References

1. K. S. MUKHERJEE, P. K. GHOSH and SAH BADRUDDOJA, *Phytochemistry*, 1981, 20, 1441.
2. K. S. MUKHERJEE, P. K. GHOSH and M. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Phytochemistry*, 1982, 21, 2416.
3. K. S. MUKHERJEE, P. K. GHOSH and R. K. MUKHERJEE, *Phytochemistry*, 1983, 22, 1296.
4. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 219.
5. "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Eyre & Spottiswoode Publishers Ltd., London, 1965, Vol. I, p. 228.
6. K. S. MUKHERJEE and P. K. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 850.
7. J. S. MILLS and A. E. WERNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3132.

Chemical Investigation of the Whole Plant of *Erigeron canadensis*

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ERIGERON canadensis (Compositae) is known¹ to be used in diarrhea, dysentery, kidney affections etc. Bohlmann *et al*² isolated a cumulene derivative from the plant. The present investigation reports the isolation of a sterol mixture shown to be α -spinasterol (stigmasta-7,22-diene-3 β -ol) and stigmast-7-en-3 β -ol and a steroidal ketone mixture shown to be stigmasta-7,22-dien-3-one and stigmast-7-en-one.

Experimental

The plant material was collected during January to April from Burdwan district in West Bengal.

Extraction and Isolation of constituents: Dried and powdered whole plant of *E. canadensis* (2 kg) was extracted with light petrol (b.p. 60-80°) for 12 h in a soxhlet apparatus. Evaporation of the solvent yielded a crude extract (28 g), which on chromatography on a column of silica gel yielded two solids, Solid A (4 g), m.p. 168-170° as the less polar component, and Solid B (2 g), m.p. 164-166° as the more polar constituent.

Solid B: The physical properties of the more polar Solid B and its acetate were very close to those of α -spinasterol (stigmasta-7,22-dien-3 β -ol) and its acetate³. Solid B acetate does not depress the m.p. of α -spinasteryl acetate.

	M.p.	[α] _D
Solid B	164-166°	0°
Acetate	174-176°	0°
α -Spinasterol	170-172°	-4°
Acetate	175°	-3.5°

However, the mass spectrum of Solid B acetate (M⁺ 456 and 454) indicated⁴ it to be a mixture of the acetates of α -spinasterol and stigmast-7-en-3 β -ol. We failed to resolve the acetate mixture even on a column of silica gel impregnated with silver nitrate, but could chemically prove it to be a mixture of the above two compounds.

It is known⁵ that the Δ^{22} -double bond of α -spinasteryl acetate can be preferentially reduced on catalytic hydrogenation but the Δ^7 -double bond is simultaneously rearranged to $\Delta^{8(14)}$ -position to yield stigmast-8(14)-en-3 β -yl acetate and that stigmast-7-en-3 β -yl acetate rearranges⁶ to stigmast-8(14)-en-3 β -yl acetate under the same condition. Accordingly, the acetate of Solid B was shaken in